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Companies Offering Formal Training Globally

Declined by an average of 6.18% between 2013 and 2022 for the countries considered.

The indicator "Companies Offering Formal Training" measures the percentage of companies that offer formal training programs to their employees. This type of training includes structured and systematic educational activities designed to enhance workers' professional skills, knowledge, and abilities, in line with the company's needs. A high percentage of this indicator indicates a strong commitment by companies to invest in the continuous development of employees' skills, promoting productivity, competitiveness, and innovation capacity. The data refers to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://databank.worldbank.org/metadataglossary/world-development-indicators/series/IC.FRM.TRNG.ZS#:~:text=Firms%20offering%20formal%20training%20are,permanent%2C%20full%2Dtime%20employees.>

Companies Offering Formal Training Globally in 2022. The analysis of the data on companies offering formal training as a percentage reveals a significant disparity between countries, highlighting the importance of continuous training for skill development and economic competitiveness. China stands out with 100% of companies offering formal training, indicating a total commitment to employee skill development and innovation. This result could be attributed to the strong emphasis placed by the Chinese government and companies on continuous training as a means to support economic growth and maintain a competitive advantage globally. Latin American countries like Ecuador (92.5%), Peru (81.9%), and Colombia (77.9%) also show high levels of participation in formal training, indicating a growing awareness of the importance of professional training in the region. These data suggest an improvement in educational policies and greater investment by companies in human capital. In Europe, France (84.6%) and Luxembourg (82.1%) rank among the countries with the highest percentages, reflecting a long-standing tradition of supporting professional training and continuous learning. Sweden (76.4%) and Ireland (73.5%) follow with high percentages, confirming the importance attributed to training in the European context to maintain a qualified and innovative workforce. However, it is surprising to note that countries traditionally considered advanced in terms of education and skill development, such as Denmark (47.3%) and Finland (60.4%), show relatively lower percentages compared to other European nations. This could indicate a variation in training strategies, where informal training or other skill development methods might play a more prominent role. In Africa, the percentages vary considerably. Countries like Ghana (46.7%) and Kenya (43%) are in a relatively good position, suggesting a growing commitment to professional training. However, most African countries, such as Nigeria (33.8%), Uganda (39.3%), and Burundi (35.6%), show lower percentages, indicating significant challenges in implementing

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formal training programs. These countries might face obstacles such as lack of resources, inadequate infrastructure, and economic barriers that limit access to training. It is evident that greater international support and stronger national policies might be needed to improve the situation of formal training in these countries. In Asia, the discrepancies are equally evident. Mongolia (82.3%) and the Philippines (73.5%) show high levels of participation in training, while other countries like India (40.9%) and Pakistan (35.6%) have much lower percentages. Indonesia (2.5%), with an extremely low percentage, represents a worrying case, suggesting that formal training is widely neglected, which could limit skill development and innovation opportunities in the country. These data highlight the need for significant investments and policy reforms to improve access to and quality of professional training in many Asian countries. In Latin America, while some countries show high percentages, others like El Salvador (65.3%) and Nicaragua (70.1%) present more modest levels. This variability may be due to different levels of economic development, investments in the education sector, and government policies supporting training. It is interesting to note that emerging economies, such as Bolivia and Honduras (57%), show a considerable commitment to formal training, suggesting they are trying to bridge the skills gap to improve their economic competitiveness. In Europe, countries like Slovenia (52%), Slovakia (51%), and Austria (50.1%) show percentages around half, indicating that, despite the recognized importance of training, there is still room for improvement to increase access and participation in formal training programs. Countries like Poland (21.6%) and Greece (21.4%) show much lower percentages, which could reflect economic and social difficulties limiting investment in professional training. Italy, with a percentage of 9.1%, is among the countries with the lowest percentage of companies offering formal training. This figure is particularly alarming for a nation with an advanced economy and a critical need for innovation and skill development to remain competitive. The reasons for this low level of training could be manifold, including labor market rigidity, lack of investment in human capital, and a possible disconnection between the education system and labor market needs. This scenario requires urgent intervention by the Italian authorities to incentivize companies to invest more in training their employees. Countries like South Africa (2.7%) and Egypt (2.7%) show an extremely critical situation, with almost non-existent formal training percentages. This suggests severe deficiencies in educational systems and labor policies, which could significantly hinder long-term economic development and growth. The lack of formal training can lead to a less qualified workforce, reducing productivity and innovation capacity in these countries.

Companies Offering Formal Training Globally between 2013 and 2022. The analysis of data related to companies offering formal training between 2013 and 2022 reveals significant variations between different countries, highlighting a heterogeneous picture of development and regression. Starting with the countries with the highest increases, Pakistan shows impressive growth, rising from 2.5% to 35.6%, with an absolute increase of 33.1 percentage points, equal to a percentage change of 1324%. This figure suggests robust development of educational infrastructures and increased investment in formal training by companies. Nepal and Azerbaijan follow with percentage changes of 596.08% and 423.29%, respectively, showing significant increases indicating a growing awareness of the importance of formal training for improving work skills. India recorded an increase of 192.14%, rising from 14% to 40.9%, demonstrating remarkable progress, although the absolute increase is lower than the top three countries. This development can be attributed to targeted government policies and increased private sector investment in training. Georgia also saw significant growth of 191.80%, followed by Albania and North Macedonia with changes of 189.47% and 153.93%, respectively, highlighting a positive regional trend in the Balkans. Countries like Hungary and Uzbekistan showed

more modest but still relevant increases, of 153.17% and 145.90%, respectively. In Africa, countries like Ivory Coast and Cameroon saw important growths of 124.44% and 66.54%, respectively, suggesting a progressive improvement in educational policies and professional training. However, not all countries saw increases. Some registered significant decreases. China and Ukraine, for example, showed no changes (0%), indicating a stagnation in the proportion of companies offering formal training. Worse still, countries like Slovenia and Croatia saw declines of -2.62% and -4.81%, respectively, signaling slight regression. There are also countries with more marked decreases. Argentina, for example, saw a decline of 36.33%, dropping from 73.5% to 46.8%, which may reflect economic problems or a reduction in company investment in training. The Czech Republic and Bulgaria recorded even greater declines of 37.62% and 40.74%, respectively, indicating possible systemic challenges or a growing disinterest in formal training. The most drastic declines are observed in countries like the Russian Federation and the Arab Republic of Egypt, with decreases of 86.34% and 87.26%, respectively. This could result from political unrest, economic crises, or radical changes in educational policies. Thailand recorded a decrease of 81.29%, while South Africa saw a decline of 93.25%, dropping from 40% to 2.7%, indicating an almost total collapse of the formal training offer.

Conclusions. On average, the percentage of companies offering formal training decreased by 6.18% between 2013 and 2022 in the countries considered, dropping from 40.7 units to 38.2 units. It should be noted that some countries, however, have seen a very significant increase in the percentage of companies offering formal training, such as Pakistan with +1324.00%, Nepal with +596.00%, Azerbaijan with +423.29%, India with +192.14%, Georgia with +191.80%. There are also countries where the percentage of companies offering formal training programs has decreased much more than the average, such as Malaysia with -69.66%, Thailand with -81.29%, Russia with -86.34%, Egypt with -87.26%, South Africa with -93.25%. Looking at Western countries with medium-high per capita income, we can see that the percentage of companies offering formal training tends to be above 50.00%.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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